

THE IMPORTANCE OF PRONUNCIATION IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND PROSPECTS OF IMPROVING PRONUNCIATION COMPETENCE

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Abstract. *The purpose of this scientific article is to clarify how important it is to pronounce words correctly when learning a foreign language. This topic has been discussed many times by many linguists, and on the basis of all important approaches, correct pronunciation guidelines are now being taught to literate people. This article reveals many important aspects of pronunciation competence as an example. As the object of the article, tools and methods were taken to form pronunciation competence and develop it. Analysis of the guidelines for the use of the same tools and methods is the subject of the work. Monographs and scientific articles completed in our linguistics were used as a theoretical source for the work.*

Key words: *competence, pronunciation, communication, speaking skills, phoneme, tongue twisters, podcasts, speech pattern.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПРОИЗНОШЕНИЯ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРОИЗНОСИТЕЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ

Аннотация. *Цель данной научной статьи – выяснить, насколько важно правильно произносить слова при изучении иностранного языка. Эта тема неоднократно обсуждалась многими лингвистами, и на основе всех важных подходов сейчас преподаются рекомендации по правильному произношению грамотных людей. В данной статье на примере раскрываются многие важные аспекты произношенной компетентности. В качестве объекта статьи были взяты средства и методы формирования произносительной компетенции и ее развития. Предметом работы является анализ рекомендаций по использованию одних и тех же средств и методов. В качестве теоретического источника для работы были использованы монографии и научные статьи, выполненные по нашему языкознанию.*

Ключевые слова: *компетентность, произношение, общение, разговорные навыки, фонема, скороговорки, подкасты, речевой образец.*

INTRODUCTION

“The time has come to create in Uzbekistan a new system of teaching foreign languages, which will become a solid foundation for the future. Since we set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must be fluent in at least two foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the work of the head of each education institution”, Shavkat Mirziyoyev said.

Within the current setting of expanded globalization, the pertinence of knowing outside dialects has heightened altogether. As companies are developing past topographical boundaries and abroad travel is more achievable, viably connection with people from different social settings has turned into an imperative capacity for victory. This piece will expound on why learning remote dialects holds awesome importance and ought to be emphasized more in a proficient setting.

The key advantage of securing a remote dialect is that it permits you to speak with people from diverse countries. Being able to talk within the local dialect of your clients or partners may cultivate a more strong believe relationship and can contribute towards an moved. It moreover permits you to get it their culture, values, and trade hones, which can be basic in today's globalized economy.

Moreover, thinks about have appeared that learning a remote dialect can make strides your communication abilities in your local dialect. By learning a modern dialect, you gotten to be more mindful of sentence structure, language structure rules, and lexicon, which can improve your composing and talking capacities in your possess dialect.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Pronunciation is the way in which a word or a dialect is talked. This may allude to for the most part agreed-upon arrangements of sounds utilized in talking a given word or dialect in a particular lingo ("adjust" or "standard" elocution) or essentially the way a specific person talks a word or dialect.

Pronunciation is the way in which we create the sounds of a dialect. It is an fundamental component of dialect learning since it influences how well we are able communicate with others.

On the off chance that our articulation is destitute, we may battle to be understood, even in case our language structure and lexicon are rectify. This will lead to disappointment and a need of certainty in talking the dialect. In expansion to influencing our capacity to communicate, articulation too plays a pivotal part in tuning in comprehension. On the off chance that we cannot listen the sounds of a dialect accurately, we may battle to get it what others are saying. This could make it troublesome to lock in in discussions and can ruin our dialect learning advance.

At long last, pronunciation can influence our capacity to be caught on by others. On the off chance that we have a overwhelming complement or mispronounce words, local speakers may battle to get it us. This will be disappointing for both parties and can prevent our capacity to construct connections with local speakers. Having great articulation can bring numerous benefits to dialect learners. Firstly, it can make strides our certainty in talking the dialect. In case we will articulate words and expressions accurately, we are more likely to feel confident in our capacity to communicate with others.

This could lead to a more positive language learning encounter and can encourage us to proceed learning. Great pronunciation can too move forward our tuning in comprehension. In the event that we will listen the sounds of a dialect accurately, we are more likely to get it what others are saying. This can make it less demanding to lock in in conversations and can progress our in general dialect learning advance.

At long last, great articulation can improve our capacity to be understood by others. In the event that we are able talk clearly and precisely, local speakers are more likely to get it us. This will make it less demanding to construct connections with native speakers and can offer assistance us to coordinated into the culture of the dialect we are learning.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Numerous individuals who finding how to memorize English as a moment language come up against a really baffling issue! They ponder difficult to be able to talk with adjust language

structure, exact lexicon and important expressions. However when they talk, they still in some cases listen reactions like:

“I'm too bad, what?”

“Could you rehash that please?”

It's greatly irritating! In case your English elocution isn't great, at that point your level of familiarity will be reliably thought little of. A solid complement can be an extraordinary barrier to making associations. Investigate indeed appears that bosses within the US regularly favor candidates who talk with standard forms of British and American complements for more prestigious parts. One thing is for beyond any doubt: working on your elocution aptitudes is certainly worth the exertion.

How to move forward pronunciation:

1. Center on phonemes
2. Look YouTube for tips from individual learners
3. Try some tongue twisters
4. Learn new words with their pronunciation
5. Read aloud and record yourself
6. Listen to some podcasts
7. Speak slowly
8. Spend more time to talking with native speakers

➤ *CENTER ON PHONEMES*

It can be accommodating to go back to nuts and bolts and look at the sounds utilized in English words. This doesn't cruel singing the letter set once more — you likely learned that a long time prior! It implies learning the English phonemes.

What are phonemes? Well, you will have taken note that numerous letters are articulated in an unexpected way on their claim than when they are utilized in words. Numerous letters contain more than one sound – “F” for occurrence is articulated “e fff”. Phonemes are the smallest unit of sound within the English dialect — the sounds that letters contain when broken down.

➤ *LOOK YOU TUBE FOR TIPS FROM INDIVIDUAL LEARNERS*

There are a few troublesome sounds that are beautiful one of a kind to English, and articulating them will be troublesome for non-native speakers. As Bounce the Canadian specified, your local dialect might not have made a difference you create the muscles fundamental to create these distinctive sounds. The great news is simply aren't alone in this! Whichever letter combinations, expressions or words you're battling with, other dialect learners along with your local dialect have battled with them as well!

➤ *TRY SOME TONGUE TWISTERS*

If you are unable to produce the necessary sounds for English pronunciation, you may have to exercise your mouth and tongue muscles. Pronunciation exercises like "tongue twisters" can be a fantastic method to enhance your English skills, as they consist of humorous sentences that are very challenging to pronounce correctly initially.

➤ *LEARN NEW WORDS WITH THEIR PRONUNCIATION*

If you're practicing vocabulary and come across a word that you have no idea how to pronounce, do not try to guess. It is far easier to learn the correct pronunciation from the beginning than to fix a bad habit later on. Look words up for free on a site such as:

- Dictionary.com if you are learning an American English accent.
- Dictionary.cambridge.org if you are learning a British English accent.

If you find a word particularly difficult to pronounce, you can even try recording the correct pronunciation on your phone to listen back to later.

➤ READ ALOUD AND RECORD YOURSELF

According to Bob the Canadian, it is beneficial to use your phone to record yourself while practicing pronunciation. Find a word that is difficult for you and locate a tv show, film, or YouTube video featuring a native speaker using it in a sentence. Listen to the pronunciation multiple times, and then demonstrate it by recording yourself speaking.

Some individuals also benefit from practicing while looking at their reflection in a mirror to ensure their mouth and lip movements are accurate. Listen closely to both recordings, identify what needs to be corrected, and make another attempt. Keep practicing the exercise until you are satisfied with the way the phrase sounds. Although it may be tedious, carefully practicing challenging words is a crucial part of improving pronunciation.

➤ LISTEN TO SOME PODCASTS

Listening abilities are essential for acquiring correct pronunciation in a different language because it involves observing how native speakers speak and imitating their rhythms.

Podcasts are an excellent way to become acquainted with English as it is actually spoken.

Many times, individuals are recorded in their bedrooms and studies chatting casually with their friends. Certain apps and websites, such as YouTube, allow you to listen at a slower speed, which can help you concentrate on the sounds and grasp accents more thoroughly.

SPEAK SLOWLY

Once you have identified the specific sounds you need to improve and made adjustments to your mouth or tongue when needed, you have completed the majority of the mental effort required to alter your accent. Now, the key is to master the new sounds instinctively – exchanging your previous speaking patterns for fresh ones.

Slowing down your usual speaking speed will make this stage easier, allowing you more time to consider the new rules you have studied. Even though it may be a little annoying to slow down your speech, taking the time to carefully select the correct pronunciations you have learned will help them be more easily remembered in the future.

SPEND MORE TIME TO TALKING WITH NATIVE SPEAKERS

Talking to native speakers is by far the most effective method to reduce your accent when speaking a foreign language. Consider this: how many times have you unconsciously started speaking like a friend, adopting their speech patterns or slang?

Speaking to your English speaking friend directly about your accent can be truly beneficial.

They have the ability to identify words you pronounce differently and assist you in recognizing mistakes that are not audibly discernible to you.

Specifically, the placement of emphasis on words in sentences varies among different languages. Collaborate with your partner to identify key sounds to work on and request them to

correct you if you make a mistake. If you feel too self-conscious to ask your English-speaking friend for pronunciation assistance, consider scheduling sessions with a Preply tutor. They have experience guiding other students through similar mistakes and can create a set of personalized exercises tailored to your specific requirements.

CONCLUSION

According to current research, pronunciation is a fundamental aspect of speaking and serves as the foundation for the enhancement of other speech activities. Success in mastering oral speech greatly influences the effectiveness of pronunciation. Correct pronunciation is a crucial aspect of speech culture and, as a result, an individual's overall cultural development. If the speaker does not follow the phonetic norms of the language, the listener may find it difficult or impossible to understand the speech. If the listener lacks pronunciation skills, they will struggle to understand another person's speech. Furthermore, lacking knowledge of phonetics hinders students' comprehension of contemporary writing and grammar. A strong pronunciation aspect of students' speech helps them get ready for engaging in speaking exercises.

Understanding phonetic skills will help students correctly pronounce all English sounds and distinguish between different sound qualities (clearness and regularity). Phonetic abilities are important for students to understand the rhythm of English phrases, including the stress on key words and auxiliary verbs in negative sentences. Pronunciation errors disrupt the main purpose of language, which is to facilitate communication and mutual understanding. Acquiring pronunciation skills is crucial for mastering the practical aspects of pronunciation mechanics, pronunciation speed, and developing speaking abilities.

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